

LAO PDR CLEWs Model Documentation

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1 Overview

Agriculture remains a cornerstone of Lao PDR's economy and rural livelihoods, contributing over 15% to national GDP and employing the majority of the population (Lao Statistics Bureau, 2023). However, the sector faces rising challenges due to land degradation, limited irrigation coverage, climate variability, and fragmented planning. The expansion of cash crops such as cassava and maize has intensified land-use pressure, while increasing demands on water and energy systems (World Bank, 2022; WFP, 2020).

Policy efforts to promote climate-resilient agriculture and rural electrification are often pursued in isolation. Land-use decisions rarely account for water availability, and irrigation schemes may not consider energy requirements or long-term sustainability. This fragmented approach makes it difficult to address interlinked risks, such as seasonal water scarcity, yield losses, or energy access gaps in rural areas (IWMI, 2022; IRENA, 2021).

To overcome these challenges, many countries have adopted the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems) modelling framework as a decision-support tool. For example, Ethiopia used CLEWs to guide its Climate-Resilient Green Economy Strategy by evaluating trade-offs between hydropower expansion and irrigation. Kenya applied CLEWs to examine synergies between agriculture, energy, and water access in arid regions. In Mauritius, CLEWs supported national planning on water security and renewable energy, while Nicaragua and the Dominican Republic used CLEWs to balance land-use decisions with forest conservation and biofuel development.

This project aims to identify key gaps in land, energy, and smart agriculture planning in Lao PDR, and to demonstrate the value of adopting CLEWs as an integrated modelling tool. The framework enables policymakers to explore alternative policy scenarios, test trade-offs, and design resource-efficient development strategies that align with national goals for food security, climate resilience, and sustainable land management.

1.1 The CLEWs methodology

The pursuit of sustainable development objectives requires management of an intricate web of interwoven challenges, issues and concerns. Our societies and natural environment consist of highly interlinked systems that depend on, and interact with, each other. These interactions are highly complex and decisions that impact these systems will need to be taken while facing significant uncertainties. One of the means at our disposal for addressing complexity and uncertainty is to use mathematical models.

Models have been applied to inform policies for decades in a wide range of sectors and circumstances. These approaches are generally still applicable when formulating policies under the principles of sustainable development. However, the integrated nature of the sustainable development challenge has implications for how the models should be incorporated into decision-making and policy formulation processes. It also highlights the need for conducting more integrated and cohesive policy assessments either through harmonized use of separate methodologies or development of more cross-cutting and integrated frameworks.

The CLEWs tool is a customisable modelling tool designed for this purpose. It is a methodology for integrated assessment of resource systems that provide a means to analyze and assess the interlinkages that exist among energy, water and agricultural systems as well as their impacts on - and vulnerability to - climate change. It is designed to help identify and quantify the trade-offs and synergies that may exist in simultaneous pursuit of policy goals in each area to support a coherent and cohesive process for strategy and policy formulation. CLEWs incorporates a representation the relevant bio-physical processes of the energy-land-water-climate systems as well as a techno-economic representation of the human infrastructure and value chains that rely on, and interact with, these systems. It thereby provides a means to explore how decisions (investments, strategies, technology choice) made in pursuit of

development goals in these areas compare across systems, sectors and goals. It allows for optimization of asset acquisition and operation and for assessing trade-offs and benefits among different goals.

Figure 1. Conceptual CLEWs diagram.

1.2 The initiative

UNDESA has supported around 20 countries to incorporate the CLEWs tool into different planning and policy mechanisms, such as national development plans, nationally determined contributions and sectoral policies and strategies. In the CCG universe, UNDESA is currently supporting the government of Laos, in collaboration with the Laos country partnership team of the Climate Compatible Growth Programme (CCG) and KTH Royal Institute of Technology.

The programme aims at expanding and consolidating capacity in the use of the CLEWs framework to support Lao PDR's integrated resource planning. It builds upon the knowledge shared through the energy planning work conducted in the country by CCG (using the OSeMOSYS tool) and expands its scope onto impacts of and on the availability of land and water resources under climate constraints. The intended outcome of the programme is the establishment of a core team of experts across government, utilities and academia who may own and use a fully-fledged CLEWs-Lao PDR model, further develop it, and run scenario analyses with it, in response to planning questions as they come.

2 Model scope

The CLEWs-Lao PDR model was created jointly by the National University of Laos, UNDESA and KTH, as part of the UNDESA-funded technical assistance programme. For the energy-system part of the model, previous model infrastructure created by Imperial College London and a national core working group in Lao PDR in the scope of the CCG programme was used. The model's structure was determined and its data collected over two stakeholder workshops and a series of online interactions between modellers. It is a linear optimisation model. It uses a cost minimisation approach to identify the system configuration with the lowest cost over a model horizon, subject to a set of constraints. The model divides Laos into three zones—Northern (NOR), Central (CEN), and Southern (SOU). Below is a summary of the model scope:

Sectors: Land, energy, water.

Time resolution: 8 timeslices (classified into two seasons (dry and wet), with each day split into four dayparts: Night 22-6, Interim 1 7-9, Interim 2 10-18, and Peak 19-21).

Time horizon: 2021-2055. Historical years (2021–2023) inside the modelling period.

Spatial resolution: divided in 3 geographical regions (North, Centre, and South).

3 Model structure

This section details the structure of the integrated CLEWS-Lao PDR model. It is divided into 3 sub-sections: energy, land-use, and water. Each sub-section provides a snapshot of the underlying representation of the relevant sector in the the CLEWS model.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the CLEWS-Lao PDR model.

3.1 Energy

The energy sector is represented by a set of input fuels (e.g. biomass, natural gas), transformation technologies (e.g. power plants, electricity transmission), and sectoral demands (e.g. diesel in the agricultural sector, electricity in the industry sector). Below is a simplified schematic of the power sector representation in the model. Hydropower plants and generation assets were assigned to these zones based on geographic location. Following the same approach and, as described in [1], for the cases when full spatial metadata were not available, capacity was allocated proportionally using national statistics and historical generation shares. A temporal resolution of eight time slices was used, to represent the wet and dry seasons. Additionally, four daily time divisions were introduced to capture the variation in the daily demand profile and generation from variable renewable energy (VRE) technologies. The modelled time horizon is from 2021 until 2055. The projections for the local electricity demand are obtained from estimates provided by Électricité du Laos (EDL).

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the energy system part of the CLEWs-Lao PDR model.

3.2 Land-use

The land-use sector is represented as land allocated to 10 different uses/land cover types: Agriculture, Barren land, Forests, Grasslands, Shrubland, Built-up land, Industrial Plantation, Swidden cultivation, Water bodies, and other land. Below is a schematic of the land-use sector representation in the CLEWS model.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the land use part of the CLEWs-Lao PDR model.

3.2.1 Agriculture

- 108 technologies represent different crop combinations per region.
- 1 mode of operation.
- 9 crop demands at the national level.

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of the structure of agricultural production in the CLEWs-Lao PDR model.

3.2.2 Main assumptions for crop inputs

Crop yield data was primarily sourced from the Lao PDR National Statistics website. However, this data did not distinguish between high- and low-input farming or between rainfed and irrigated crops. To classify them, insights from stakeholders at the National University of Laos were used to estimate the proportions of irrigated versus rainfed crops and high versus low input levels. Yield data for beans, coffee, maize, rubber, and rice was obtained from the GeoCLEWs tool, while yields for fruits, cassava, sugarcane, and vegetables were estimated using national data and assumed ratios for irrigation and input levels (these assumption were made based in GeoCLEWs results for other crops).

Table 1. Assumptions on input levels, high (H) and low (L), for crops across the three regions – North, Center and South.

	North				Central				South			
Beans	Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%	
	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 10%	L: 90%
Cassava	Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%	
	H: 40%	L: 60%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 40%	L: 60%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 40%	L: 60%	H: 10%	L: 90%
Coffee	Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%	
	H: 80%	L: 20%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 80%	L: 20%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 80%	L: 20%	H: 10%	L: 90%
Fruits	Rainfed 50%		Irrigated 50%		Rainfed 50%		Irrigated 50%		Rainfed 50%		Irrigated 50%	
	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%
Maize	Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%	

	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%
Lowland	Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%	
rice	H: 80%	L: 20%	H: 60%	L: 40%	H: 80%	L: 20%	H: 60%	L: 40%	H: 80%	L: 20%	H: 60%	L: 40%
Upland rice	Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%	
	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%	H: 70%	L: 30%
Rubber	Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%		Rainfed 99%		Irrigated 1%	
	H: 60%	L: 40%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 60%	L: 40%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 60%	L: 40%	H: 10%	L: 90%
Sugarcane	Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%		Rainfed 70%		Irrigated 30%	
	H: 40%	L: 60%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 40%	L: 60%	H: 10%	L: 90%	H: 40%	L: 60%	H: 10%	L: 90%
Vegetables	Rainfed 10%		Irrigated 90%		Rainfed 10%		Irrigated 90%		Rainfed 10%		Irrigated 90%	
	H: 90%	L: 10%	H: 90%	L: 10%	H: 90%	L: 10%	H: 90%	L: 10%	H: 90%	L: 10%	H: 90%	L: 10%

3.2.3 Other land uses

6 additional technologies that represent other land uses: Barren land, Forests, Grasslands, Shrubland, Built-up land, Industrial Plantation, Swidden cultivation, Water bodies, Other land.

3.2.4 Naming of technologies.

Figure 6 illustrates the naming convention for land use and land cover technologies in the model. In Appendix 1 the main naming conventions for the water and land system entries used in the OSeMOSYS interface and corresponding description is described.

Figure 6. Naming convention for land use and land cover technologies.

3.3 Water

Figure 7 represents the links between the agricultural and water systems in the model.

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of links between the water and land systems in the model.

4 Key assumptions

4.1 Socio-economic trends

Population (millions)

Source: Energy Outlook 2022

Table 2. Assumptions on population growth (millions).

2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050	2055
7.32	7.87	8.48	9.14	9.84	10.60	11.42	12.24

GDP growth (%)

Source: IMF for historical data and projections up to 2030. Own assumption from 2030.

Table 3. Assumptions on GDP growth (%).

2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050	2055
-0.4	4.0	4.8	5.8	6.8	7.8	8.8	9.8

4.2 Energy system

Demands (Pentajoules)

Source: Électricité du Laos (EDL) and following the methodology in [1].

Table 4. Assumptions on final electricity demand (PJ).

Commodity		2021	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050	2055
NORELC	Electricity demand in the northern region	9.73	23.11	25.77	29.26	33.86	39.82	49.22	58.42
CENELC	Electricity demand in the central region	13.78	22.01	29.34	34.95	41.67	50.31	62.5	74.47

SOUELC	Electricity demand in the southern region	7.34	13.55	26.36	32.73	38.97	47.7	59.31	70.68
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Powerplants – existing capacity (GW)

Source: Électricité du Laos (EDL) and following the methodology in [1].

Table 5. Existing capacity of power plants (GW).

Technology	Code	2021
Coal	PWRCOA	1.88
Biomass	PWRBIO	0.11
Solar PV	PWRSOL	0.06
Hydro	PWRHYD	8.09
Total		10.14

4.3 Land system

Land area by land use in 2021 (1000 sq km)

Source: Consultation with national stakeholders and own analysis.

Table 6. Assumptions on land covers and land use by region (1000 sq km)¹.

Technology	Code	NOR	CEN	SOU
Grassland	LNDGRA	1.44	0.90	0.80
Water bodies	LNDWAT	0.60	2.15	1.17
Built-up land	LNDBLT	0.26	0.57	0.21
Forest land	LNDFOR	49.79	41.16	28.18
Industrial plantation	LNDPLA	1.11	1.31	1.29

¹ Please refer to Figure 6 and Appendix 1 for a description of the naming conventions.

Shrubland	LNSHR	0.35	5.25	6.23
Swidden cultivation	LNSWI	1.05	0.19	0.13
Barren lands	LNSBAR	0.01	1.81	0.04
Agricultural land	LNSAGR	6.16	12.06	5.98
Others	LNSOTH	37.67	17.33	7.04

Crops: harvested area and production (2021)

Source: Yields and Residual Capacities were obtained using the GeoCLEWs tool, data from Lao PDR National Statistics (<https://laosis.lsb.gov.la/main.do>) and were then Calibrated with an Excel tool provided.

Table 7. Assumptions on crop yields in 2021².

Crop code	Crop name	Production (Mton)	Area harvested (1000 sq.km)	Yield (t/ha)
LNDBEAHICEN	CRPBEA	0.02	0.00	1.16
LNDBEAHINOR	CRPBEA	0.04	0.00	1.04
LNDBEAHISOU	CRPBEA	0.00	0.00	1.04
LNDBEAHRcen	CRPBEA	0.04	0.00	1.05
LNDBEAHRNOR	CRPBEA	0.09	0.01	0.95
LNDBEAHRsou	CRPBEA	0.01	0.00	0.94
LNDBEALICEN	CRPBEA	0.03	0.02	0.19
LNDBEALINOR	CRPBEA	0.06	0.04	0.17
LNDBEALISOU	CRPBEA	0.00	0.00	0.17
LNDBEALRCEN	CRPBEA	0.06	0.04	0.18
LNDBEALRNOR	CRPBEA	0.14	0.09	0.16
LNDBEALRSOU	CRPBEA	0.01	0.01	0.16

² Please refer to Figure 6 and Appendix 1 for a description of the naming conventions.

LNDCASHICEN	CRPCAS	0.02	0.00	5.68
LNDCASHINOR	CRPCAS	0.04	0.00	9.09
LNDCASHISOU	CRPCAS	0.05	0.00	11.14
LNDCASHRCEN	CRPCAS	4.30	0.13	3.31
LNDCASHRNOR	CRPCAS	8.40	0.16	5.30
LNDCASHRSOU	CRPCAS	11.86	0.18	6.50
LNDCASLICEN	CRPCAS	0.06	0.00	1.89
LNDCASLINOR	CRPCAS	0.11	0.00	3.03
LNDCASLISOU	CRPCAS	0.15	0.00	3.71
LNDCASLRCEN	CRPCAS	2.15	0.19	1.10
LNDCASLRNOR	CRPCAS	4.20	0.24	1.77
LNDCASLRSOU	CRPCAS	5.93	0.27	2.17
LNDCOFHICEN	CRPCOF	0.00	0.00	0.48
LNDCOFHINOR	CRPCOF	0.00	0.00	0.61
LNDCOFHISOU	CRPCOF	0.00	0.00	0.49
LNDCOFHRCEN	CRPCOF	0.01	0.01	0.22
LNDCOFHRNOR	CRPCOF	0.10	0.04	0.28
LNDCOFHRSOU	CRPCOF	1.58	0.70	0.22
LNDCOFLICEN	CRPCOF	0.00	0.00	0.16
LNDCOFLINOR	CRPCOF	0.00	0.00	0.20
LNDCOFLISOU	CRPCOF	0.01	0.01	0.16
LNDCOFLRCEN	CRPCOF	0.00	0.00	0.06
LNDCOFLRNOR	CRPCOF	0.01	0.01	0.08
LNDCOFLRSOU	CRPCOF	0.11	0.18	0.06
LNDFRUHICEN	CRPFRU	1.82	0.07	2.56
LNDFRUHINOR	CRPFRU	2.51	0.09	2.66

LNDFRUHISOU	CRPFRU	1.36	0.07	2.00
LNDFRUHRCEN	CRPFRU	1.60	0.07	2.25
LNDFRUHRNOR	CRPFRU	2.21	0.09	2.34
LNDFRUHRSOU	CRPFRU	2.78	0.16	1.76
LNDFRULICEN	CRPFRU	0.26	0.03	0.85
LNDFRULINOR	CRPFRU	0.36	0.04	0.89
LNDFRULISOU	CRPFRU	0.19	0.03	0.67
LNDFRULRCEN	CRPFRU	0.23	0.03	0.75
LNDFRULRNOR	CRPFRU	0.32	0.04	0.78
LNDFRULRSOU	CRPFRU	0.40	0.07	0.59
LNDMAIHICEN	CRPMAI	0.56	0.07	0.75
LNDMAIHINOR	CRPMAI	1.46	0.22	0.67
LNDMAIHISOU	CRPMAI	0.01	0.00	0.82
LNDMAIHRcen	CRPMAI	1.18	0.17	0.68
LNDMAIHRNOR	CRPMAI	3.09	0.51	0.61
LNDMAIHRsou	CRPMAI	0.65	0.09	0.74
LNDMAILICEN	CRPMAI	0.08	0.03	0.25
LNDMAILINOR	CRPMAI	0.21	0.09	0.22
LNDMAILISOU	CRPMAI	0.00	0.00	0.27
LNDMAILRCEN	CRPMAI	0.17	0.07	0.23
LNDMAILRNOR	CRPMAI	0.44	0.22	0.20
LNDMAILRSOU	CRPMAI	0.09	0.04	0.25
LNDRICLOHICEN	CRPRIC	6.63	0.82	0.81
LNDRICLOHINOR	CRPRIC	1.71	0.19	0.91
LNDRICLOHISOU	CRPRIC	2.80	0.39	0.71
LNDRICLOHRCEN	CRPRIC	14.17	2.55	0.55

LNDRICLOHRNO R	CRPRIC	3.66	0.58	0.63
LNDRICLOHRSOU	CRPRIC	5.98	1.22	0.49
LNDRICLOLICEN	CRPRIC	1.47	0.55	0.27
LNDRICLOLINOR	CRPRIC	0.38	0.13	0.30
LNDRICLOLISOU	CRPRIC	0.62	0.26	0.24
LNDRICLOLRCEN	CRPRIC	1.18	0.64	0.18
LNDRICLOLRNOR	CRPRIC	0.30	0.15	0.21
LNDRICLOLRSOU	CRPRIC	0.50	0.31	0.16
LNDRICUPHICEN	CRPRIC	0.00	0.00	0.45
LNDRICUPHINOR	CRPRIC	0.01	0.01	0.12
LNDRICUPHISOU	CRPRIC	0.00	0.00	0.32
LNDRICUPHRCEN	CRPRIC	1.47	0.09	1.59
LNDRICUPHRNO R	CRPRIC	0.03	0.57	0.01
LNDRICUPHRSOU	CRPRIC	0.11	0.09	0.12
LNDRICUPLICEN	CRPRIC	0.00	0.00	0.09
LNDRICUPLINOR	CRPRIC	0.00	0.00	0.09
LNDRICUPLISOU	CRPRIC	0.00	0.00	0.05
LNDRICUPLRCEN	CRPRIC	0.01	0.04	0.04
LNDRICUPLRNOR	CRPRIC	0.09	0.24	0.04
LNDRICUPLRSOU	CRPRIC	0.01	0.04	0.02
LNRUBHICEN	CRPRUB	0.00	0.00	0.09
LNRUBHINOR	CRPRUB	0.00	0.00	0.09
LNRUBHISOU	CRPRUB	0.00	0.00	0.05
LNRUBHRCEN	CRPRUB	0.08	1.47	0.05
LNRUBHRNOR	CRPRUB	0.08	1.47	0.05

LNRUBHRSOU	CRPRUB	0.05	1.47	0.04
LNRUBLICEN	CRPRUB	0.00	0.02	0.04
LNRUBLINOR	CRPRUB	0.00	0.02	0.04
LNRUBLISOU	CRPSGC	0.00	0.02	0.02
LNRUBLRCEN	CRPRUB	0.02	0.98	0.02
LNRUBLRNOR	CRPRUB	0.00	0.98	0.00
LNRUBLRSOU	CRPRUB	0.02	0.98	0.02
LNSGCHICEN	CRPSGC	0.02	0.00	0.90
LNSGCHINOR	CRPSGC	0.04	0.00	0.94
LNSGCHISOU	CRPSGC	0.02	0.00	1.35
LNSGCHRCEN	CRPSGC	0.15	0.02	0.78
LNSGCHRNOR	CRPSGC	0.26	0.03	0.82
LNSGCHRSOU	CRPSGC	0.15	0.01	1.17
LNSGCLICEN	CRPSGC	0.08	0.02	0.33
LNSGCLINOR	CRPSGC	0.14	0.04	0.35
LNSGCLISOU	CRPVEG	0.08	0.02	0.50
LNSGCLRCEN	CRPSGC	0.13	0.04	0.29
LNSGCLRNOR	CRPSGC	0.22	0.07	0.30
LNSGCLRSOU	CRPSGC	0.13	0.03	0.43
LNDVEGHICEN	CRPVEG	4.57	0.60	0.76
LNDVEGHINOR	CRPVEG	2.49	0.31	0.81
LNDVEGHISOU	CRPVEG	5.57	0.47	1.19
LNDVEGHRcen	CRPVEG	0.04	0.07	0.07
LNDVEGHRNOR	CRPVEG	0.09	0.13	0.07
LNDVEGHRsou	CRPVEG	0.05	0.05	0.10
LNDVEGLICEN	CRPVEG	0.16	0.07	0.23

LNDVEGLINOR	CRPVEG	0.08	0.03	0.25
LNDVEGLISOU	CRPVEG	0.19	0.05	0.36
LNDVEGLRCEN	CRPVEG	0.00	0.01	0.02
LNDVEGLRNOR	CRPVEG	0.00	0.01	0.02
LNDVEGLRSOU	CRPVEG	0.00	0.01	0.03
Total			23.03	

4.4 Water system

Source: Water Balance data is from GeoCLEWs tool, assumptions made based in previous GeoCLEWs models, and input data from stakeholders in Lao PDR.

Water demand (Billion cubic meters)

Table 8. Assumptions on water demand.

Technology	Code	2021	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050	2055
Public water demand	PUBWAT	0.23	0.25	0.27	0.28	0.30	0.33	0.35	0.37

Agriculture water use (Billion cubic meters per 1000 sq km)

Table 9. Assumption on irrigation water use by crop³.

Technology	2021
LNDBEAHICEN	0.22
LNDBEAHINOR	0.13
LNDBEAHISOU	0.22
LNDBEALICEN	0.08
LNDBEALINOR	0.02
LNDBEALISOU	0.07
LNDCASHINOR	0.25

³ Please refer to Figure 6 and Appendix 1 for a description of the naming conventions.

LNDCASHISOU	0.24
LNDCASLICEN	0.16
LNDCASLINOR	0.10
LNDCASHICEN	0.31
LNDCOFHINOR	0.16
LNDCASLISOU	0.10
LNDCOFHISOU	0.19
LNDCOFLICEN	0.04
LNDCOFLINOR	0.03
LNDFRUHINOR	0.18
LNDCOFLISOU	0.01
LNDFRUHISOU	0.20
LNDFRULICEN	0.16
LNDCOFHICEN	0.21
LNDFRULINOR	0.03
LNDFRULISOU	0.03
LNDMAIHINOR	0.15
LNDMAIHISOU	0.23
LNDMAILICEN	0.08
LNDMAILINOR	0.02
LNDMAILISOU	0.08
LNDRICLOHINOR	0.22
LNDRICLOHISOU	0.29
LNDFRUHICEN	0.30
LNDRICLOLINOR	0.04
LNDRICLOLISOU	0.09

LNDRICLOLICEN	0.10
LNDRICUPHINOR	0.22
LNDRICUPHISOU	0.29
LNDRICUPLINOR	0.04
LNDRICUPLISOU	0.09
LNDRICUPLICEN	0.10
LNDRUBHINOR	0.06
LNDMAIHICEN	0.24
LNDRUBLINOR	0.05
LNDRUBHISOU	0.15
LNDRUBLISOU	0.12
LNDRUBLICEN	0.07
LNSGCHINOR	0.20
LNSGCLINOR	0.04
LNSGCHISOU	0.21
LNSGCLISOU	0.03
LNSGCLICEN	0.05
LNDRICLOHICEN	0.31
LNDVEGHINOR	0.04
LNDRICUPHICEN	0.31
LNDVEGHISOU	0.02
LNDRUBHICEN	0.14
LNDVEGLICEN	0.09
LNSGCHICEN	0.25
LNDVEGLINOR	0.04
LNDVEGHICEN	0.29

LNDVEGLISOU	0.01
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5 Scenarios

This section contains descriptions of a set of scenarios explored using the Laos-CLEWs model. The scenarios were designed based on stakeholder inputs to guide national policy and investment decisions during the 2nd CLEWs workshop in 2025 and over follow-up discussions.

5.1 Scenario 1: Afforestation

Challenge:

Deforestation and land degradation threaten carbon sinks and ecosystems in Laos. Achieving national forest restoration goals requires balancing land, water, and resource demands.

Modelling Needs:

- The model sets an afforestation target of 70% forest cover by 2030 based on the Laos Green Growth Strategy.
- CLEWs-based analysis to assess land, water, and energy trade-offs.

Policy Implications:

- Integrate afforestation targets into national land-use and climate plans.
- Consider how afforestation versus crop production targets influence available land for afforestation and other land uses.

5.2 Scenario 2: Climate-Smart Agriculture

Challenge:

Degraded soils and uncertain water availability limit agricultural productivity. Climate change exacerbates these issues, requiring more diverse, adaptive planting strategies.

Modelling Needs:

- CLEWs-based analysis to link land, water use, and crop productivity.
- Investment scenario planning for smart agricultural technologies.

Policy Implications:

- Support diversified agriculture and adaptive plant varieties.
- Consider how the uptake of new crop varieties impacts costs, land-use and water demand.

6 Results

Key results of the CLEWS-Laos model for all scenarios are presented in this section.

6.1 Baseline

6.1.1 Power generation by region

Electricity generation increases from around 46 PJ in 2021 to over 216 PJ in 2055.

Figure 8. Power generation by region (PJ) in the baseline scenario.

6.1.2 Power capacity (GW) and Power Generation (PJ) by source

Power capacity increases from around 11 GW to 39 GW, dominated by hydropower production.

Figure 9. Total capacity (left) and power generation (right) in the Baseline scenario.

6.1.3 Diesel use for agriculture (PJ)

Diesel use increases from around 1.4 PJ in 2021 to around 2.5PJ in 2055.

Figure 10. Diesel use in agriculture in the Baseline scenario (PJ).

6.1.4 CO₂ emissions from agriculture and imports (Million tons of CO₂ equivalent)

The increase in diesel use in agriculture drives the increase in CO₂ emissions, totaling around 180 million ton of CO₂eq in 2055 – corresponding to a 80% increase relative to 2021.

Figure 11. CO₂eq emissions in the Baseline scenario (Million tons).

6.1.5 Total land use per region (1000 sq km)

Harvested land for crop production increases across all regions. The land occupied by forest is the highest in North, but it shows a significant decrease in both the central and southern regions from 2021 to 2055.

Figure 12. Total land use per region (1000 sq km).

6.1.6 Irrigated vs rainfed crops

The total harvested land is the highest in the central region, increasing by 46% from 2021 to 2055.

Figure 13. Total harvested land by region (1000 sq km).

Total crop production doubles from around 14.4 Mton in 2021 to 28.8 Mton in 2055. The central region having the highest share of irrigated crop production.

Figure 14. Total crop production by region (Million tons).

6.1.7 Crop production per region

Cassava is the most produced crop in both the north and southern regions, while rice dominates production in the center.

Figure 15. Crop production by crop and by region (Million tons).

6.1.8 Crop variable costs (Million USD)

Sugarcane is the most profitable crop in terms of export value, followed by stream rice.

Figure 16. Variable crop cost (Million USD).

6.1.9 Water use per sector

Water use increases throughout the period of analysis driven by both the increase in water used for agriculture and public water demand.

Figure 17. Water use by sector (billion m³).

References

- [1] Y. Nakajima, V. Sridharan, A. Hawkes, K. Nanthavong, S. Phommachanh, and S. Pye, “Modelling the long-term risks surrounding Laos’ electricity trade,” *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 61, p. 101865, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.esr.2025.101865.

Appendix 1 Naming convention for the land and water systems

Table 10. Naming convention for the land and water systems commodities.

Commodity name	Description
AGRWAT	Water for irrigation
CRPBEA	Beans
CRPCAS	Cassava
CRPCOF	Coffee
CRPFRU	Fruits
CRPMAI	Maize
CRPRIC	Rice
CRPRICST	Stream Rice
CRPRUB	Rubber
CRPSGC	Sugarcane
CRPVEG	Vegetable
LAGR	Agricultural land
LBAR	Barren land
LBLT	Built-up land
LFOR	Forest Land
LGRA	Grassland
LND	Land
LPLA	Land for industrial plantation
LSHR	Shrubland
LSWI	Swidden cultivation land
LWAT	Water bodies
WTREVT	Evapotranspiration water
WTRGWT	Groundwater recharge

WTRPRC	Precipitation water
WTRRUN	Run-off water

Table 11. Naming convention for the land and water systems technologies.

Technology name	Description
LNDBEAHINOR	Bean High Irrigated North region
LNDBEALRNOR	Bean Low Rainfed North region
LNDBEALINOR	Bean Low Irrigated North region
LNDCASHRNOR	Cassava High Rainfed North region
LNDCASHINOR	Cassava High Irrigated North region
LNDCASLRNOR	Cassava Low Rainfed North region
LNDCASLINOR	Cassava Low Irrigated North region
LNDCOFHRNOR	Coffee High Rainfed North region
LNDCOFHINOR	Coffee High Irrigated North region
LNDCOFLRNOR	Coffee Low Rainfed North region
LNDCOFLINOR	Coffee Low Irrigated North region
LNDFRUHRNOR	Fruits High Rainfed North region
LNDFRUHINOR	Fruits High Irrigated North region
LNDFRULRNOR	Fruits Low Rainfed North region
LNDFRULINOR	Fruits Low Irrigated North region
LNDMAIHRNOR	Maize High Rainfed North region
LNDMAIHINOR	Maize High Irrigated North region
LNDMAILRNOR	Maize Low Rainfed North region
LNDMAILINOR	Maize Low Irrigated North region
LNDRICUPHRNOR	Rice upland High Rainfed North region

LNDRICUPHINOR	Rice uppland High Irrigated North region
LNDRICUPLRNOR	Rice uppland Low Rainfed North region
LNDRICUPLINOR	Rice uppland Low Irrigated North region
LNDRICLOHRNOR	Rice uppland High Rainfed North region
LNDRICLOHINOR	Rice uppland High Irrigated North region
LNDRICLOLRNOR	Rice uppland Low Rainfed North region
LNDRICLOLINOR	Rice uppland Low Irrigated North region
LNDRUBHRNOR	Rubber High Rainfed North region
LNDRUBHINOR	Rubber High Irrigated North region
LNDRUBLRNOR	Rubber Low Rainfed North region
LNDRUBLINOR	Rubber Low Irrigated North region
LNDSGCHRNOR	Sugarcane High Rainfed North region
LNDSGCHINOR	Sugarcane High Irrigated North region
LNDSGCLRNOR	Sugarcane Low Rainfed North region
LNDSGCLINOR	Sugarcane Low Irrigated North region
LNDVEGHRNOR	Vegetables High Rainfed North region
LNDVEGHINOR	Vegetables High Irrigated North region
LNDVEGLRNOR	Vegetables Low Rainfed North region
LNDVEGLINOR	Vegetables Low Irrigated North region
LNDBEAHRNOR	Bean High Rainfed Central region
LNDBEAHICEN	Bean High Irrigated Central region
LNDBEALRCEN	Bean Low Rainfed Central region
LNDBEALICEN	Bean Low Irrigated Central region
LNDCASHRCEN	Cassava High Rainfed Central region
LNDCASHICEN	Cassava High Irrigated Central region
LNDCASLRCEN	Cassava Low Rainfed Central region

LNDCASLICEN	Cassava Low Irrigated Central region
LNDCOFHRCEN	Coffee High Rainfed Central region
LNDCOFHICEN	Coffee High Irrigated Central region
LNDCOFLRCEN	Coffee Low Rainfed Central region
LNDCOFLICEN	Coffee Low Irrigated Central region
LNDFRUHCEN	Fruits High Rainfed Central region
LNDFRUHICEN	Fruits High Irrigated Central region
LNDFRULRCEN	Fruits Low Rainfed Central region
LNDFRULICEN	Fruits Low Irrigated Central region
LNDMAIHCEN	Maize High Rainfed Central region
LNDMAIHICEN	Maize High Irrigated Central region
LNDMAILRCEN	Maize Low Rainfed Central region
LNDMAILICEN	Maize Low Irrigated Central region
LNDRICUPHRCEN	Rice upland High Rainfed Central region
LNDRICUPHICEN	Rice upland High Irrigated Central region
LNDRICUPLRCEN	Rice upland Low Rainfed Central region
LNDRICUPLICEN	Rice upland Low Irrigated Central region
LNDRICLOHRCEN	Rice upland High Rainfed Central region
LNDRICLOHICEN	Rice upland High Irrigated Central region
LNDRICLOLRCEN	Rice upland Low Rainfed Central region
LNDRICLOLICEN	Rice upland Low Irrigated Central region
LNDRUBHRCEN	Rubber High Rainfed Central region
LNDRUBHICEN	Rubber High Irrigated Central region
LNDRUBLRCEN	Rubber Low Rainfed Central region
LNDRUBLICEN	Rubber Low Irrigated Central region
LNDSGCHRCEN	Sugarcane High Rainfed Central region

LNDSGCHICEN	Sugarcane High Irrigated Central region
LNDSGCLRCEN	Sugarcane Low Rainfed Central region
LNDSGCLICEN	Sugarcane Low Irrigated Central region
LNDVEGHRcen	Vegetables High Rainfed Central region
LNDVEGHICEN	Vegetables High Irrigated Central region
LNDVEGLRCEN	Vegetables Low Rainfed Central region
LNDVEGLICEN	Vegetables Low Irrigated Central region
LNDBEAHRsou	Bean High Rainfed South region
LNDBEAHISOU	Bean High Irrigated South region
LNDBEALRSOU	Bean Low Rainfed South region
LNDBEALISOU	Bean Low Irrigated South region
LNDCASHRSOU	Cassava High Rainfed South region
LNDCASHISOU	Cassava High Irrigated South region
LNDCASLRSOU	Cassava Low Rainfed South region
LNDCASLISOU	Cassava Low Irrigated South region
LNDCOFHRSOU	Coffee High Rainfed South region
LNDCOFHISOU	Coffee High Irrigated South region
LNDCOFLRSOU	Coffee Low Rainfed South region
LNDCOFLISOU	Coffee Low Irrigated South region
LNDFRUHRsou	Fruits High Rainfed South region
LNDFRUHISOU	Fruits High Irrigated South region
LNDFRULRSOU	Fruits Low Rainfed South region
LNDFRULISOU	Fruits Low Irrigated South region
LNDMAIHRsou	Maize High Rainfed South region
LNDMAIHISOU	Maize High Irrigated South region
LNDMAILRSOU	Maize Low Rainfed South region

LNDMAILISOU	Maize Low Irrigated South region
LNDRICUPHRISOU	Rice upland High Rainfed South region
LNDRICUPHISOU	Rice upland High Irrigated South region
LNDRICUPLRSOU	Rice upland Low Rainfed South region
LNDRICUPLISOU	Rice upland Low Irrigated South region
LNDRICLOHRISOU	Rice upland High Rainfed South region
LNDRICLOHISOU	Rice upland High Irrigated South region
LNDRICLOLRSOU	Rice upland Low Rainfed South region
LNDRICLOLISOU	Rice upland Low Irrigated South region
LNDRUBHRISOU	Rubber High Rainfed South region
LNDRUBHISOU	Rubber High Irrigated South region
LNDRUBLRSOU	Rubber Low Rainfed South region
LNDRUBLISOU	Rubber Low Irrigated South region
LNDSGCHRISOU	Sugarcane High Rainfed South region
LNDSGCHISOU	Sugarcane High Irrigated South region
LNDSGCLRSOU	Sugarcane Low Rainfed South region
LNDSGCLISOU	Sugarcane Low Irrigated South region
LNDVEGHRISOU	Vegetables High Rainfed South region
LNDVEGHISOU	Vegetables High Irrigated South region
LNDVEGLRSOU	Vegetables Low Rainfed South region
LNDSGCLIRISOU	Sugarcane Low Irrigated South region
LNDBLT	Built-up land
LNDWAT	Land for water bodies
LNDFOR	Forest land
LNDGRA	Grassland
LNDPLA	Land for industrial plantation

LNDSHR	Shrubland
LNDSWI	Swidden cultivation land
LNDBAR	Barren land
TRDEXPFRU	Fruits exports
TRDEXPMAI	Maize exports
TRDIMPRICST	Rice stram imports
TRDEXPRIC	Rice exports
TRDEXPRUB	Rubber exports
TRDIMPVEG	Vegetables imports